

TAILWIND

KPIs for Floating Offshore Wind/D1.2

WP1, T1.3

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Technical references

Project Acronym	TAILWIND
Project Title	Sustainable station-keeping systems for floating wind
Project Coordinator	Aligi Foglia – Zefeng Zhou NGI aligi.foglia@ngi.no – zefeng.zhou@ngi.no
Project Duration	January 2024 – December 2027 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D1.3
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP1 - Design Basis and Technology Qualification Plan
Task	T1.3 – Definition and Benchmarking of KPIs for Floating Offshore Wind
Lead beneficiary	3 (DTU)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	NGI, SINTEF, ICONS
Due date of deliverable	31 December 2024
Actual submission date	31 December 2024

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

v	Date	Reason for issue	Beneficiary	Author	Reviewed by
1.0	29/11/2024	For internal review	DTU	Athanasios Kolios	Aligi Foglia, Stian Stensby Sørnum, Alexandra Scudo
2.0	31/12/2024	Final submission	DTU	Athanasios Kolios	

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Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on key performance indicators (KPIs) that can be utilised to evaluate technological innovations and concepts of offshore wind and renewable energy projects. Migrating from the traditional LCOE-focused assessment we perform a detailed investigation of technical and economic indicators, briefly presenting the quantification relationship, relevance to the topic, advantages and limitations of each identified indicator.

We adopt a systematic literature review for a complete and reliable analysis while we introduce the following classification for each group of KPIs. For technical KPIs we identified performance and efficiency, reliability and downtime, availability and operational readiness, flexibility and grid stability, capacity and power, and finally power quality and grid compliance as subcategories. For the economic KPIs we identified cost and financial performance, profitability and return, revenue and cash flow, project time frame and performance, and financial risk and leverage KPIs as subcategories. In addition to this, we have linked identified KPIs with specific criteria that can allow benchmarking of industrial feasibility of different components.

Next, for an indicative benchmarking case study we have reduced the number of qualifying KPIs for the relative qualification of a range of configurations for floating wind turbines combining different platform types, site locations and mooring systems. The criteria that we used included mean time between failures, unplanned downtime, availability, degradation rate, capital expenditure, operational expenditure, levelized cost of energy, and system lifetime. The benchmarking study reveals that chain and steel moorings offer superior performance in shallow and deep-water scenarios, respectively, balancing reliability and operational efficiency. While cost-effective soft materials perform well in shallow-water setups, steel and stiff materials are recommended for high-tension environments due to their robustness, durability, and suitability for demanding configurations.

This deliverable has introduced a framework for the assessment of technological innovations, through a multi criteria approach, particularly applicable to floating wind energy systems and together with deliverable 5.1, that will follow, allow for a very comprehensive review of KPIs that can inform design and optimization processes in modern wind energy systems.

Acronyms and abbreviations

A = Availability
Asys = System Availability
CAPEX = Capital Expenditure
Ceff = Capital Efficiency
CF = Capacity Factor
CFaR = Cash Flow at Risk
CoR = Cost of Risk
CR = Curtailment Ratio
DPP = Discounted Payback Period
DR = Degradation Rate
DSCR = Debt Service Coverage Ratio
DtE = Debt-to-Equity Ratio
Eeff = Energy Efficiency
ELCC = Effective Load-Carrying Capability
EFOR = Equivalent Forced Outage Rate
EYR = Energy Yield Risk
FOR = Forced Outage Rate
IRR = Internal Rate of Return
LCC = Total Lifecycle Cost
LCOE = Levelized Cost of Energy
LFC = Load Following Capability
LOLE = Loss of Load Expectation
MTBF = Mean Time Between Failures
MTTR = Mean Time to Repair
NPV = Net Present Value
OPEX = Operational Expenditure
OM = Operating Margin
Pd = Power Density
PI = Profitability Index
PQ = Power Quality
RAROC = Risk-Adjusted Return on Capital
RES = Revenue from Energy Sales
ROI = Return on Investment
RPC = Reactive Power Capability
RR = Ramp Rate
RT = Response Time
SI = System Inertia
SR = Sharpe Ratio
System Lifetime = Project Life
UD = Unplanned Downtime
 λ = Failure Rate

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable aims to introduce a framework for evaluating floating offshore wind configurations and technological innovations through a combination of multi attribute key performance indicators that account for both technical and economic performance. To this end this deliverable aims to collect and categorise an extensive list of indicators that can not only be utilised for comparative purposes but can further stand as objectives for design and optimization of modern offshore wind farms.

A key element of the analysis is the classification of information into different groups and subgroups to allocate the collected KPIs. For technical KPIs we identified performance and efficiency, reliability and downtime, availability and operational readiness, flexibility and grid stability, capacity and power, and finally power quality and grid compliance as subcategories. For the economic KPIs we identified cost and financial performance, profitability and return, revenue and cash flow, project time frame and performance, financial risk and leverage, and market and external support KPIs as subcategories.

In addition to this, the KPIs that have been identified, are linked explicitly with a list of practical criteria that are suggested for the investigation and comparison of the technical feasibility of different technological anchor options. This can allow a more quantitative assessment of technological feasibility, offering more transparent assessments and reducing bias through a better structured approach.

To illustrate how these KPIs can be utilised and combined we define an indicative case study of the benchmarking of different scenarios subject to a reduced number of criteria and through a simple multi-criteria analysis method, namely weighted sum method, we qualify the optimal scenario for the defined problem. It is important to mention that this approach is best suited for the preliminary stages of projects when not all of the information is available while it can be refined further as more information becomes available and certain attributes can indeed be quantified. To this end, the outcomes of this study should be considered as illustrative only.

Although in this work we are focusing on technical and economic indicators, additional KPI categories should be taken into consideration towards a robust and complete review and analysis. Such categories include environmental and social indicators which will be covered later in deliverable D5.1 of the TAILWIND project. Together these two deliverables offer a very comprehensive review of available KPIs able to characterise the impact of TAILWIND innovations through this comprehensive yet adaptable framework and will further inform activities in subsequent work packages. In addition, this deliverable will inform activities of Task 3.1, and the evaluation of sustainable anchor concepts.

1.2 Relation to Project Objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the objectives of the TAILWIND project. More specifically Objective O2 refers to cost savings and hence relevant economic KPIs such as CapEx OpEx and LCOE allow for the detailed assessment of economic performance. Further Objective O3 which relates to impact quantification requires a multi-dimensional approach to measuring impact. As such, identifying relevant KPIs through a systematic review of literature provides the tools to measure the impact of all our innovations at a local and full scale identifying opportunities that require further focus for improvements.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is organised in six chapters. Following this brief introduction, the methodology for the KPI definition and the benchmarking approach we follow is presented. Next, the review of the technical and economic KPIs following our proposed classification is systematically presented with a short discussion on reducing the identified criteria for an illustrative benchmark study. Then, criteria are defined for the assessment of industrial feasibility of technological options, and they are linked to the KPIs identified previously. Chapter 5 presents our high-level benchmarking study on the comparison of different configurations of floaters, mooring systems and deployment sites. Finally, we round up this deliverable with some conclusions and recommendations for next steps.

2. Methodology

2.1. Approach to KPI Definition

To allow for a comprehensive consideration of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for floating offshore wind energy systems, a systematic literature review approach has been chosen, as this methodology allows for an objective and more replicable approach to collecting, classifying and reporting information available to the academic body of knowledge. Through this approach, we rely on databases, such as Scopus, which covers a vast number of peer-reviewed sources which in sequence offer reliable sources for synthesising conclusions. Core to the process is the careful and inclusive selection of keywords; in this instance we consider the following words and phrases: *KPIs, offshore wind, floating wind, renewable energy, and offshore renewable energy*. Once the relevant sources are collected, manual screening will take place for relevance and completeness based on the broader understanding developed during review.

A broad classification of KPIs, categorises *technical, economic, environmental, and societal* indicators, however in this deliverable we will focus on the first two categories of KPIs, following the proposed classification (Figure 1). A review of environmental and societal KPIs, will be addressed in WP5 and reported in 'D5.1 Key Performance Indicators Relevant to Floating Renewable Energy Systems', and ultimately, the two deliverables will be combined in a thorough review paper, potentially in collaboration with other European projects working on the same topics. The identification, selection and utilization of KPIs, is sufficient for screening a number of technological options that have been developed and further analysis will focus on subsequent WPs.

Figure 1: Classification of KPIs

2.2. Benchmarking Methodology

In this deliverable, we adopt benchmarking as a structured approach to evaluate the relative performance of identified technological options based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Given the early phases of the project, a semi-quantitative multi-criteria assessment methodology has been employed to assign relative scores (1-5) for each KPI, with 1 denoting the least favourable performance state and 5 denoting the most favourable. This approach aims to balance resource constraints and the limited information available at this stage while providing a systematic comparison of alternatives to establish performance baselines, identify potential gaps, and support informed decision-making.

In this study, the benchmarking has the purpose to illustrate the approach so the scoring of each alternative against each of the criteria was given according to the best knowledge of the authors, a combination of expert opinions, published literature and real-world data will be adopted. This approach is deemed sufficient for the objectives set and the current state of the project. The experience of the TAILWIND consortium members will provide an important source of information, ensuring a well-informed scoring process in future project activities.

The authors are aware of the limitations of such a semi-quantitative approach, hence special attention will be given to ensure that scoring reflects the actual performance, the strengths and weaknesses of each alternative, and there is no redundancy, duplication or bias. The table below, highlights the benefits and limitations of the selected approach. As the project matures, the methodology can be revisited, and the semi-quantitative approach can be refined to incorporate more quantitative processes towards more robust and accurate assessment.

Table 1: Benefits and Limitations of Selected Benchmarking Approach

Aspect	Benefits	Limitations
Structured Framework	Provides a systematic and transparent approach to evaluating technological options.	May oversimplify complex interdependencies between criteria and factors.
Relevance to KPIs	Ensures alignment of innovations with project objectives through targeted KPI-based evaluation.	Selection and weighting of criteria may involve subjective judgment, leading to potential bias.
Data Sources	Leverages a mix of empirical data, literature insights, and expert experience for a well-rounded analysis.	Variability in data availability for certain technologies, particularly emerging ones.
Adaptability	Semi-quantitative scoring allows flexibility to refine assessments as new data emerges.	Early-stage innovations may lack comprehensive empirical data, introducing uncertainties.
Efficiency	Enables relative scoring (1-5), facilitating quick comparisons across multiple alternatives.	Simplified scoring may not capture nuanced performance differences fully.

3. KPIs for Floating Offshore Wind Systems

3.1. Technical KPIs

3.1.1. Performance and Efficiency KPIs

This category of KPIs focus on the actual output performance of a wind farm. Capacity factor (CF) measures the electricity generated to the maximum generation based on the installed capacity, i.e., calculated assuming that the asset functioned at its maximum capacity over the investigated period of time (Wilkie & Galasso, 2022), with a higher CF denoting a system that is maximising installed capacity for production (Boretti, 2020). Energy efficiency (E_{eff}), or Energy capture efficiency evaluates how effectively the input energy is converted into output energy (Timmons et al., 2022) (Kolosok et al., 2021), introducing changes in the design and operation of assets towards increasing production outcome. Ramp rate (RR) refers to the speed at which a renewable energy system can increase or decrease its power output (Areed et al., 2024) and represents the slope at which power changes, and it can be positive (ramp-up event where the power increases from one time step to the next one) or negative (ramp-down event where the power decreases) (D'Amico et al., 2022).

3.1.2. Reliability and Downtime KPIs

Offshore wind systems need to withstand harsh environmental conditions and are located at a distance from shore, making intervention a complex process, hence monitoring reliability through appropriate KPIs is a key priority. Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) is a statistical measure that evaluates the average time that a system functions before it stops due to a failure (Scheu, 2012). Closely associated with MTBF is the failure rate, denoted as λ , and which measures how often a component, assembly, or entire system fails during operation (Ghaedi & Gorginpour, 2021). In general, λ is connected to MTBF, using the formula $\lambda = 1/\text{MTBF}$. These are two key reliability metrics that are derived through operational data or established databases and are used for developing maintenance strategies and suggesting design improvements (Carroll et al., 2016). Another associated metric is the Mean Time To Repair (MTTR), which statistically captures the average time it takes to repair a system following a failure (Maheshwari & Ramakumar, 2019) and offers an indication of the maintainability of the system, considering factors such as accessibility, logistics or maintenance procedures (Zare Oskouei & Mohammadi-Ivatloo, 2020).

To describe the state of an asset not operating, we introduce the critical metric of Unplanned Downtime (UD), which refers to the time when the system is unexpectedly non-operational, caused by various factors such as equipment failures or maintenance delays (Trempe et al., 2024). Analysing downtime, offers insights on how it can be reduced through better planning of potential interventions, leading to increased availability which is another key metric that will be presented later (Koukoura et al., 2021). It is important to note that downtime does not account for periods where the asset is not producing due to lack of the natural resource, i.e. wind. Finally, the metrics of Forced Outage Rate (FOR) and Equivalent Forced Outage Rate (EFOR), indicate the portion of time that the system is out of service due to unforeseen

issues like mechanical failures or grid disruptions with the later also considering the system's overall capacity (Weijie et al., 2022) (Chaiamarit & Nuchprayoon, 2013), with higher values signalling reduced reliability and decreased energy production.

3.1.3. Availability and Operational Readiness KPIs

The important metric of Availability (A) accounts for the portion of time that a wind turbine or farm is able to produce energy (Cevasco et al., 2021). This metric is closely linked with downtime, and in fact is measured as the ratio of uptime (time that the asset can operate) divided by the total time, which is the sum of uptime and downtime. A high value denotes high production and in general high profitability. Availability, which can be calculated with some variations based on the definition of downtime, is a key metric as it is normally introduced to contractual agreements between parties to ensure that sufficient capacity can enter the grid in any given instance. Availability is engineered into a system as a result of reliability and maintainability. It can be measured at a component, sub-system or full-system level (Das et al., 2021) (M. N. Scheu et al., 2017).

3.1.4. Flexibility and Grid Stability KPIs

Flexibility and grid stability indicators, account for the ability of energy systems to adjust to the demand requirements, considering that large wind farms are part of the broader electricity mix. The metric of Response Time (RT) measures the time that a system can adjust to shifts in input conditions, i.e. due to environmental changes like wind speed (Xu et al., 2023), with higher values denoting more adaptable systems (Saeedi et al., 2013). On the other hand, System Inertia (SI) measures the ability that an energy system can resist to changes in grid frequency (Shu et al., 2024). Inertia can result from the rotating mass of a turbine rotor and maintaining frequency stability is crucial; hence introduction of technologies such as storage may need to be integrated to the system. The Curtailment Ratio (CR) is an indicator that measures the potential energy production that is wasted due to grid limitations or oversupply due to excessive wind (Yasuda et al., 2022). Reducing CR is important as when turbines rotate without feeding the grid with energy, they consume their fatigue life without generating useful energy. To this end, storage technologies are also relevant against wasting energy due to curtailment.

3.1.5. Capacity and Power KPIs

This category of KPIs is employed to evaluate the efficiency of energy systems in terms of energy output and space utilisation. Starting from Power density (Pd), this metric measures the amount of power produced per unit area or volume (J. Zhang et al., 2023). To this end, number and spacing of units within a wind farm is crucial, also considering restrictions from other uses of the sea for offshore installations, so achieving high power density is an indication of increased space efficiency (Abe et al., 2022). Focusing on the time-varying performance of assets, the Degradation Rate (DR) estimates the decline in performance of components or systems as the asset ages (Olczak, 2023). This is associated with varying levels of reliability throughout the service life of the assets, increased cost for maintenance and potentially reduction in energy production and profitability (Meyers et al., 2020). Considering the ability of a system to contribute to peak demand periods, Effective Load-Carrying Capability (ELCC) is a key metric which denotes capability to consistently produce during times of high demand, factor which is particularly relevant to intermittent energy sources like wind so that they can meet grid standards (Ghazal et al., 2021). Finally, Loss

of Load Expectation (LOLE) is a metric that calculates the hours within a period where an energy system cannot meet energy demand (Yu et al., 2019), informing operators of the need for backup or alternative power sources to meet energy needs (Avdijaj et al., 2024).

3.1.6. Power Quality and Grid Compliance KPIs

Power Quality and Grid Compliance KPIs measure how well the electricity produced by a power generation system meets grid standards. Power Quality (PQ) is a primary metric that measures how stable and consistent power generated is considering voltage, and frequency (X.-P. Zhang & Yan, 2020) (Bajaj & Singh, 2020). Potentially, it can also be linked to curtailment. It is an important measure not only considering meeting the demand, but also for preventing equipment and devices downstream from getting damaged. Finally, Reactive Power Capability (RPC), serves as an indicator of how well an energy system can supply or absorb reactive power (Bhatt et al., 2020), which is essential for managing voltage levels and maintaining grid stability, as without proper control equipment can be damaged and even blackouts be caused (Othman & Al-Yozbaky, 2022).

Table 2: Technical KPIs - Performance and Efficiency KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Capacity Factor (CF)	The ratio of the actual energy output to the maximum possible energy output over a period.	Percentage (%)	Capacity Factor = (Actual Output / Maximum Output) * 100	Capacity factor indicates the efficiency of a renewable energy system, with higher values indicating better performance.	Indicates system efficiency and actual performance; Useful for comparing different energy technologies	Highly dependent on resource availability (e.g., wind, solar); Does not reflect grid demand alignment
Energy Efficiency (E_{eff})	The ratio of useful energy output to total energy input.	Percentage (%)	Energy Efficiency = (Useful Energy Output / Total Energy Input) * 100	Energy efficiency measures how effectively a system converts input energy into useful output, a critical performance indicator in renewable systems.	Measures how effectively a system converts energy input to output; Important for assessing overall system performance	Ignores operational costs and reliability; Requires careful data collection for input-output comparison
Ramp Rate (RR)	The rate at which a system can increase or decrease its power output.	Power per time (e.g., MW/min)	Ramp Rate = Δ Power Output / Δ Time	Ramp rate is important for grid integration, especially for systems like wind and solar, which need to adjust output based on fluctuating conditions.	Critical for assessing system flexibility and ability to adapt to grid fluctuations; Useful in grid integration analysis	High ramp rate can strain mechanical systems; Ignores long-term energy production efficiency

Table 3: Technical KPIs - Reliability and Downtime KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)	The average time between system failures, used to measure reliability.	Time (hours, days)	$MTBF = \text{Total Operational Time} / \text{Number of Failures}$	MTBF is key for reliability analysis, especially in systems where failure can lead to significant downtime and repair costs.	Critical for measuring reliability and failure predictability; Helps improve maintenance schedules	Requires extensive historical data; Does not account for the severity of failures
Mean Time to Repair (MTTR)	The average time required to repair a system after a failure.	Time (hours, days)	$MTTR = \text{Total Repair Time} / \text{Number of Repairs}$	A lower MTTR indicates faster recovery from failures, enhancing the system's overall availability and performance.	Measures maintenance efficiency and system recovery time; Helps optimize repair processes	Ignores the frequency of failures; Low MTTR might not offset frequent failures
Failure Rate (λ)	The rate at which failures occur in a system, typically measured over time or operational cycles.	Failures per time period	$\text{Failure Rate} = \text{Number of Failures} / \text{Total Operating Time}$	Failure rate is essential for understanding system reliability and is often used in conjunction with MTBF to assess performance.	Quantifies the frequency of system failures; Essential for long-term reliability assessments	Focuses only on failure frequency, ignoring impact or severity; Needs extensive data for accuracy
Unplanned Downtime (UD)	The time when the system is unexpectedly offline due to failures or other issues.	Time (hours, days)	$\text{Unplanned Downtime} = \text{Total Downtime} - \text{Scheduled Downtime}$	Minimizing unplanned downtime is key for maximizing energy production and improving system reliability.	Highlights reliability issues that affect operational efficiency; Useful for improving maintenance strategies	Ignores planned maintenance and other downtime factors; Does not capture performance during available time
Forced Outage Rate (FOR)	The percentage of time a system is unavailable due to unplanned outages.	Percentage (%)	$FOR = (\text{Forced Outage Time} / \text{Total Time}) * 100$	FOR highlights the frequency and impact of unplanned outages, which directly affect energy production and system reliability.	Identifies unscheduled downtime, which affects overall energy production; Useful for identifying reliability issues	Does not consider planned outages; May overestimate operational risk in systems with minimal forced outages
Equivalent Forced Outage Rate (EFOR)	EFOR measures the percentage of time a system is unavailable due to forced outages, adjusted for system capacity.	Percentage (%)	$EFOR = (\text{Forced Outage Time} / \text{Total Available Time}) * 100$	EFOR provides a more precise measure of system downtime, taking capacity constraints into account.	Adjusts for system capacity to provide a more accurate measure of reliability; Important for identifying underperforming units	Requires detailed outage and capacity data; Does not capture overall system performance

Table 4: Technical KPIs - Availability and Operational Readiness KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Availability (A)	The percentage of time a system is operational and available to generate energy.	Percentage (%)	Availability = $(\text{Total Operational Time} / \text{Total Time}) * 100$	Availability is crucial for assessing the reliability of a system, particularly in offshore energy projects where downtime can be costly.	Measures the system's operational reliability; Useful for assessing downtime and maintenance impacts	Ignores energy production efficiency during available time; Doesn't account for performance during operational hours
System Availability (A_{sys})	The percentage of total operational time a system is available to produce energy, including scheduled and unscheduled downtime.	Percentage (%)	System Availability = $(\text{Available Time} / \text{Total Time}) * 100$	Higher system availability directly improves energy output and financial returns, making it a critical metric for assessing reliability.	Provides a holistic view of system uptime, including planned and unplanned downtime; Essential for operational planning	Ignores system performance when available; Does not differentiate between types of downtime

Table 5: Technical KPIs - Flexibility and Grid Stability KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Response Time (RT)	The time taken by a system to react to a change in input or external conditions.	Time (seconds, minutes)	Response Time = Time to Reach Steady State After Input Change	Shorter response times improve system adaptability and are critical for maintaining grid stability in dynamic conditions.	Measures how quickly a system adapts to changes in input or demand; Important for grid balancing and dynamic conditions	Ignores total system efficiency; Not always crucial for renewable energy projects with intermittent resources like wind or solar
System Inertia (SI)	Refers to the ability of the system to resist changes in frequency, providing stability to the grid.	Unitless	-	System inertia is crucial for maintaining grid stability, especially as renewable penetration increases.	Important for ensuring grid stability and frequency control; Key for understanding the impact of renewable integration on the grid	Difficult to measure accurately in systems without rotating mass; Irrelevant for standalone or non-grid-tied systems
Curtailement Ratio (CR)	Measures the percentage of potential energy generation that is curtailed due to grid or system limitations.	Percentage (%)	Curtailement Ratio = $(\text{Energy Curtailed} / \text{Total Potential Energy}) * 100$	Curtailement Ratio is key for evaluating how much energy is lost due to grid restrictions or oversupply.	Quantifies energy losses due to grid constraints or oversupply; Useful for optimizing grid integration of renewables	Ignores potential revenue loss from curtailment; Highly dependent on grid management and infrastructure

Table 6: Technical KPIs - Capacity and Power KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Power Density (P_D)	The amount of power generated per unit area or volume.	Power per area (e.g., W/m ²)	Power Density = Power Output / Area	Power density is crucial for comparing different renewable energy technologies, especially in space-constrained environments like offshore wind farms.	Useful for comparing land-use efficiency across technologies; Important for evaluating space-constrained installations	Can disadvantage renewable systems with lower density (e.g., solar); Does not consider energy yield or grid value
Degradation Rate (DR)	The rate at which system performance decreases over time, often due to wear or environmental factors.	Percentage per year (%)	Degradation Rate = (Initial Performance - Performance After Time) / Time	Degradation rate is important for long-term system performance, particularly for technologies like solar panels and wind turbines.	Important for long-term performance forecasting; Helps estimate replacement and maintenance needs	Highly variable across different technologies and locations; Requires continuous monitoring for accuracy
Effective Load-Carrying Capability (ELCC)	ELCC assesses the ability of a renewable energy system to contribute reliably to peak load conditions.	Percentage (%)	ELCC = (Capacity Provided at Peak Load / Total Installed Capacity) * 100	ELCC is crucial for understanding how much a renewable energy system can be relied upon during peak demand times.	Quantifies how much of a renewable system's capacity can reliably meet peak demand; Key for assessing grid contribution	Can be difficult to calculate for variable resources like wind and solar; Ignores total energy generation potential
Loss of Load Expectation (LOLE)	LOLE estimates the number of hours or days in a year when the system will be unable to meet demand.	Time (hours, days)	LOLE = Σ (Probability of Demand Exceeding Supply) over Time	Critical for understanding system reliability and planning backup resources.	Provides insight into the reliability and adequacy of energy systems; Important for grid planning and backup power assessments	Assumes constant demand, which may not reflect real-world scenarios; Does not account for the severity of shortfalls

Table 7: Technical KPIs - Power Quality and Grid Compliance KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Power Quality (PQ)	Assesses the stability and consistency of the electricity generated in terms of voltage, frequency, and waveform.	Percentage (%)	PQ = (Number of Disturbances / Total Time) * 100	PQ is essential for ensuring renewable systems meet grid standards for power delivery.	Assesses the stability of power output in terms of voltage, frequency, and waveform; Critical for grid compliance	Does not measure total energy output; Difficult to manage in systems with variable output like wind and solar
Reactive Power Capability (RPC)	Measures the system's ability to supply reactive power, which is necessary for voltage control on the grid.	MVAR (Mega Volt-Ampere Reactive)	Reactive Power Capability = (Available Reactive Power / Maximum Reactive Power) * 100	Essential for voltage regulation and maintaining grid reliability, particularly in high-renewable systems.	Critical for maintaining voltage stability in the grid; Ensures grid reliability and reduces the risk of voltage sags or surges	Does not measure real power output; Complex to manage in systems without inherent reactive power capability, like solar PV

3.2. Economic KPIs

3.3.1. Cost and Financial Performance KPIs

This category of indicators denotes measures that evaluate the requested expenditure to develop an asset and keep it up and running considering uncertainties. The first KPI considered is Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) which includes all costs prior to commissioning of the asset, such as planning, acquisition, manufacturing and installation, while often costs such as decommissioning are also accounted for in this indicator (Sens et al., 2022a). Contrary to conventional power generation, wind energy assets refer to front-loaded investments hence a higher-than-expected CAPEX can determine feasibility of an investment (Proost, 2019). More specifically, the DEVEX KPI represents the initial costs associated with planning, feasibility studies, permitting, and design activities, providing a critical measure of early-stage investments required to move the project forward (Sens et al., 2022b). Once the asset is commissioned and starts producing power, additional expenses need to be considered to operate and maintain it for the 25+ years of its operation, and this is reflected in the OPEX metric (Yildiz et al., 2024), hence this expense is distributed over the service life of the asset. OPEX is strongly linked with a number of technical KPIs that were presented earlier in this chapter, such as those related to reliability and operators aim to optimise through-life performance in order to minimise OPEX (Kolios et al., 2020).

The combination of CAPEX and OPEX combined (together with decommissioning costs which include labour, transportation, waste management and environmental cleanup (Jadali et al., 2021)) account for the Total Lifecycle Cost (LCC) (Yang et al., 2024), another important metric that can be used to determine an investment or event compare between different technological options. The cost indicators presented earlier provide absolute cost values, without taking into account the power produced; hence, the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) is introduced as a metric that represents the average cost of power unit throughout the asset's life span (Shen et al., 2020), combining CAPEX, OPEX and generated power. LCOE is another typical metric that is used for comparison of different technologies and configurations (Ioannou et al., 2018).

In addition to the cost indicators presented earlier, Cost of Financing (CoF) and Cost of Risk (CoR) are two indicators that are particularly relevant to offshore wind investments due to the intensity of capital required and the significant uncertainties involved in such projects. CoF accounts for the cost of securing the required funds throughout the project's lifetime, such as interest rates to repay debts (Neuhoff et al., 2022). CoR, on the other hand, accounts for the impact of risks such as market volatility, environmental variations or operational issues in financial terms, predicting financial losses for the developers.

3.3.2. Profitability and Return KPIs

This category of KPIs assist in determining the potential financial returns and attractiveness of an investment, and they are often used in conjunction with the indicators mentioned in the previous section. Considering that between the project conception to decommissioning, a period of 30 years may pass, so Net Present Value (NPV) accounts for the real value of money of cashflows, bringing all expenses in a specific time instance, to allow comparison of options for expenditure. This adjustment is achieved through a specific discount rate,

which accounts for market forces and cost of financing (Kulkarni et al., 2022). Associated with NPV is the Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which estimates the value of the discount rate/rate of return that results to the marginal zero NPV (Al Hasibi & Haris, 2023). NPV can be an indication of profitability of an investment (Ioannou et al., 2018), if its value is positive. Similarly, if IRR exceeds the cost of capital the investment is profitable and both can be used for comparison of technological options (Finke et al., 2023). A similar metric, in the form of a ratio, is the Return on Investment (ROI), which quantifies how many times does the net profit returns the initial investment (Osiolo, 2021); hence, the highest the value ROI the more profitable the investments (Raugei, 2019). In literature, the metric of Profitability Index (PI) is also present as a cost-benefit ratio between a project's payoff and its initial investment (Forero-Quintero et al., 2022) (Brodziński et al., 2021). Finally, Operating Margin (OM) is a metric that presents the revenue that remains after covering all expenses, with a higher OM denoting a more profitable project (Sharma & Shrestha, 2006).

As mentioned earlier, the uncertainties inherent into offshore wind applications (i.e. market fluctuations, regulatory changes, and operational risks) should be accounted for, hence metrics such as Risk-Adjusted Return on Capital (RAROC) are important to quantify the financial impact of these risks on profitability (Liu et al., 2021). Additionally, different metrics are employed to account for the efficiency of utilising the wind farm as an asset or the capital investment. Return on Assets (ROA) is a measure of how efficiently a project uses its assets to generate profit, calculated as the ratio between net income by the total value of the assets (Takashima, 2018). With respect to how efficiently a project generates returns with respect to the invested capital, a higher Capital Efficiency (Ceff) denotes a project producing more revenue/profit for the money invested. Both metrics are particularly relevant to capital intensive technologies such as offshore wind. Finally, the Sharpe Ratio (SR) is a key metric that assesses returns relative to the risks taken within an investment, comparing the excess return to the level of volatility due to external factors, with higher SRs suggesting projects with strong returns compared to the risks taken (Wang et al., 2024) (Bai et al., 2023).

3.3.3. Revenue and Cash Flow KPIs

This category of indicators assesses the liquidity and ability of the project to cover operational and debt-related obligations and hence the short- and long-term financial performance and sustainability of a project. Revenue from Energy Sales (RES) is a key metric of financial performance impacting cashflow and profitability and focuses on the absolute value of income from selling electricity to the grid (Qi et al., 2024). Influencing factors include rated capacity, market prices and power purchase agreements (PPAs) in place (Phan et al., 2024). A tool and a metric that is relevant here is also the Cash Flow Analysis (CFA) which is employed to analyse cash inflows and outflows throughout the lifetime of the project, ensuring that financial obligations are met and financial risks are managed (Perrelli et al., 2023). Finally, similarly to the previous category of indicators, Cash Flow at Risk (CFaR) is used to incorporate uncertainties in the analysis of cashflows (Vaianti et al., 2017). Both CFA and CFaR are very relevant in the early stages of investments when CAPEX is high and revenues are even more critical (before reaching the breakeven point).

3.3.4. Project Timeframe and Performance KPIs

The duration of an investment/project is also particularly important as this can also affect the attractiveness of the investment. Modern offshore wind farms are designed for a Project or System Lifetime of approximately 25+ years, often with an outlook for lifetime extension

(Kim, 1996). During this time, the asset should generate power and create revenues that will cover the initial investment allowing for profit. The duration of the project will affect a number of indicators presented earlier, including LCOE, NPV, and ROI. Although operators tend for longer lifetimes, the increasing cost of operation and maintenance in the later stage of a project should be factored in the analysis to ensure that the generated profits justify the incurred expenses. A relevant metric here is the Discounted Payback Period (DPP) which indicates the amount of time that is needed to recover the initial investment, adjusted for the real time of value through the NPV concept (Janíček et al., 2019), with the shorter DPP denoting an investment with faster recovery of the invested capital (Mohan et al., 2022).

3.3.5. Financial Risk and Leverage KPIs

Considering that offshore wind projects require significant funding, often sought from external sources, quantifying financial risks through appropriate KPIs is essential. To this end, Debt-to-Equity (DtE) ratio accounts for the relative proportion between debt and equity that are utilised to finance a project (Cilesiz & Dayi, 2023). Depending on the relative risks of a project, relying on equity rather than debt could be a preferred option, offering a share to shareholders rather than borrowing money with the obligation of repaying with interest (Alexander-Haw & Breitschopf, 2024). Once debt is involved to an investment, Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR) is the metric that indicates the ability of a project to fulfil the debt obligations, combining the net operating income with the total debt service (Firouzi & Meshkani, 2021) (Roy et al., 2024). WACC calculates the average cost of a project's financing by combining the weighted proportions of equity and debt, serving as a key indicator of financial feasibility and influencing project valuation metrics like NPV and IRR (Ghigo et al., 2020). Finally, considering uncertainties that are present in the investment, and linked to the power produced and hence the resulting profit, Energy Yield Risk (EYR) measures and compares the actually generated energy with the forecasted values, so accurate resource assessment and income forecasting is of paramount importance to reduce EYR and meet financial and operational expectations.

Table 8: Economic KPIs - Cost and Financial Performance KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Total upfront costs to develop and install the energy system.	Currency (e.g., \$/MW)	CAPEX = Equipment Cost + Installation Cost + Grid Connection Cost + Other Fixed Costs	Important for evaluating the initial financial burden of the project, influencing investor decisions.	Captures upfront costs for financial feasibility; Critical for budgeting and project finance.	High CAPEX can be a barrier; Ignores long-term OPEX; Increases financial risk.
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Costs related to the operation and maintenance of the system over time.	Currency (e.g., \$/MW/yr)	OPEX = Annual Maintenance Costs + Operational Costs + Insurance + Taxes	Critical for long-term financial sustainability and identifying cost reduction opportunities.	Assesses long-term operational costs; Identifies efficiency improvements; Ensures project sustainability.	Unpredictable maintenance costs; Varies by location and technology; High OPEX erodes profitability.
Total Lifecycle Cost (LCC)	Includes CAPEX, OPEX, and decommissioning costs.	Currency (e.g., \$/MW over lifetime)	LCC = CAPEX + Σ OPEX + Decommissioning Cost	Provides a full cost assessment over the system's lifecycle, necessary for long-term sustainability evaluation.	Offers a complete view of project costs; Ensures long-term planning; Captures hidden costs for sustainability analysis.	Requires accurate future cost data; High lifecycle costs can deter investors; Significant cost variation by location.
Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)	The cost of generating electricity, taking into account both CAPEX and OPEX over the system's life.	Currency (e.g., \$/kWh)	LCOE = (CAPEX + Σ OPEX) / (Σ Energy Produced Over Lifetime)	The most widely used metric for comparing cost-effectiveness between energy technologies.	Combines CAPEX, OPEX, and other costs; Useful for cost comparisons; Commonly used metric in energy markets.	Ignores externalities like subsidies; Overlooks timing of energy generation; Can be misleading if used alone.
Cost of Financing	Interest rates, loan terms, and other factors impacting project financing costs.	Percentage (%)	Cost of Financing = Interest Rate * Loan Amount	Financing costs are essential in calculating overall project viability and affordability.	Shows full financial burden; Affects project cost structure; Lower costs improve NPV and IRR.	Subject to interest rate fluctuations; High financing costs reduce profitability; Hard to secure favourable terms.
Cost of Risk (CoR)	Quantifies the financial cost of risks associated with the project.	Currency (e.g., \$/MWh)	CoR = (Risk Exposure * Probability of Occurrence) / Energy Produced	Provides a clear understanding of the cost impact of potential risks on project economics.	Quantifies financial impact of risks; Improves risk management strategies; Helps justify mitigation costs.	Difficult to assess accurate probabilities; Highly dependent on risk estimation; External factors may affect risk outcomes.
Development Expenditure (DEVEX)	Costs incurred before construction, including feasibility studies, permitting, and design.	Currency (e.g., \$/MW)	DEVEX = Feasibility Study Cost + Permitting Cost + Design and Planning Cost	Crucial for project planning and approval, influencing whether the project proceeds.	Captures early-stage investment; Supports feasibility analysis; Improves project accuracy.	May be high in complex or regulated environments; Costs can vary significantly by region.

Table 9: Economic KPIs - Profitability and Return KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Net Present Value (NPV)	The value of cash inflows minus the value of cash outflows, discounted over the project's lifetime.	Currency (e.g., \$)	$NPV = \sum (\text{Cash Inflow} - \text{Cash Outflow}) / (1 + \text{Discount Rate})^t$	Assesses whether the project generates a positive return, critical for decision-making.	Incorporates all future cash flows; Considered a gold standard for investment decisions; Accounts for time value of money.	Sensitive to discount rates; Requires accurate cash flow projections; No return percentage provided.
Internal Rate of Return (IRR)	The discount rate that makes the net present value (NPV) of all cash flows from a project zero.	Percentage (%)	$\sum (\text{Cash Flow} / (1 + \text{IRR})^t) = 0$, where t is the time period	IRR allows for comparing project profitability across different investment opportunities.	Measures project profitability; Considers time value of money; Helps gauge project viability.	Can be misleading for varying durations; Unrealistic cash flow reinvestment assumptions; Multiple IRRs may exist.
Return on Investment (ROI)	Measures the gain or loss generated on an investment relative to its cost.	Percentage (%)	$ROI = (\text{Net Profit} / \text{Investment Cost}) * 100$	Simple metric for measuring overall profitability, useful for attracting investors.	Simple and intuitive; Quick profitability snapshot; Widely recognized.	Ignores time value of money; Overlooks long-term cash flows; Misleading without risk context.
Profitability Index (PI)	Ratio of payoff to investment, showing the relationship between costs and benefits.	Ratio	$PI = \text{Present Value of Future Cash Flows} / \text{Initial Investment}$	Helps assess whether a project generates sufficient future cash flows relative to its costs.	Simplifies cost-benefit comparison; Useful in capital-constrained environments; Identifies profitable projects.	Doesn't measure actual dollar returns; Ignores absolute project size; Can favour small but inefficient projects.
Operating Margin (OM)	Measures the percentage of revenue that remains after covering operating expenses.	Percentage (%)	$\text{Operating Margin} = (\text{Operating Income} / \text{Revenue}) * 100$	Reflects the profitability of a project by comparing revenue to operating costs.	Shows operational profitability; Reflects management efficiency; Critical for performance benchmarking.	Ignores interest, taxes, and non-operational costs; Can vary significantly between industries; Does not reflect total profitability.
Risk-Adjusted Return on Capital (RAROC)	Measures the return on investment considering financial risks.	Percentage (%)	$RAROC = (\text{Expected Return} - \text{Economic Capital Charge}) / \text{Economic Capital}$	Helps quantify risk-adjusted profitability, useful for comparing projects with different risk profiles.	Adjusts profitability for risk; Useful for comparing risk-return profiles; Helps justify project risk.	Requires accurate risk assessment; Less useful for projects with non-financial risks; Not widely used or understood.
Return on Assets (ROA)	Measures how efficiently a project uses its assets to generate profit.	Percentage (%)	$ROA = \text{Net Income} / \text{Total Assets}$	Key for understanding how well a project utilizes its total asset base for generating returns.	Measures asset efficiency; Useful for evaluating capital-intensive projects; Identifies high-performing assets.	Ignores leverage and risk factors; Varies by industry norms; Can be misleading for asset-heavy renewable technologies.

Capital Efficiency (C_{eff})	Assesses the return generated per unit of capital invested.	Ratio	Capital Efficiency = Project Revenue / Total Capital Investment	Useful for comparing the efficiency of different renewable energy technologies in using capital.	Measures return on capital investment; Crucial for comparing technology efficiency; Encourages capital optimization.	Overlooks operational efficiency; Ignores long-term risks; Doesn't account for external financial conditions.
Sharpe Ratio	Adjusted return per unit of risk, comparing return to volatility.	Ratio	Sharpe Ratio = (Return of Asset - Risk-Free Return) / Standard Deviation of Asset's Return	Provides insight into how much excess return is received for the risk taken.	Measures risk-adjusted return; Useful for comparing projects with different risk levels; Highlights risk-reward balance.	Ignores absolute return potential; Assumes normal distribution of returns; Sensitive to volatility measurement errors.

Table 10: Economic KPIs - Revenue and Cash Flow KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Revenue from Energy Sales (RES)	The income generated by selling the electricity produced.	Currency (e.g., \$/MWh)	Revenue = Energy Produced * Selling Price	Key for assessing the project's income stream, directly impacting financial performance.	Directly impacts cash flow and profitability; Key for assessing economic viability; Critical for financial returns.	Revenue volatility from price fluctuations; Dependent on grid contracts; Renewable variability reduces revenue predictability.
Cash Flow Analysis	Projection of future inflows and outflows to assess liquidity and financial health.	Currency (varies)	Net Cash Flow = Σ Cash Inflows - Σ Cash Outflows	Ensures that the project remains financially solvent during its operation, critical for ongoing viability.	Detailed view of cash inflows and outflows; Essential for liquidity management; Helps optimize financial strategies.	Renewable cash flows can be unpredictable; Focuses on short-term liquidity; Complex to model.
Cash Flow at Risk (CFaR)	Measures the potential shortfall in expected cash flow due to risk factors.	Currency (e.g., \$)	CFaR = Expected Cash Flow - Value at Risk (VaR)	Critical for risk management, assessing the worst-case cash flow scenario under given conditions.	Assesses potential shortfalls in cash flow; Helps optimize liquidity management; Useful for risk-adjusted planning.	Requires sophisticated risk modelling; May underestimate long-term risks; Complex and resource-intensive to compute.

Table 11: Economic KPIs - Project Timeframe and Performance KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Project Life (System Lifetime)	The expected operational lifetime of the system.	Time (years)	-	Longer lifetimes improve cost-efficiency and influence overall financial metrics like LCOE and NPV.	Longer life improves profitability; Important for long-term planning; Advantageous for long-lifetime technologies.	Long systems require more maintenance; Uncertainty in tech advancements; Replacement costs reduce returns.
Discounted Payback Period (DPP)	Time needed to recover the initial investment, considering the time value of money.	Time (years)	$DPP = \text{Year when } \sum (\text{Discounted Cash Flow}) > \text{Initial Investment}$	Shows how long the project takes to become profitable; key for risk assessment.	Accounts for time value of money; Assesses capital recovery risk; Provides clear ROI timeline.	Ignores post-payback cash flows; Biased toward short-term projects; Undervalues long-term returns.

Table 12: Economic KPIs - Financial Risk and Leverage KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DtE)	The ratio of financing through debt versus equity.	Ratio	$\text{Debt-to-Equity Ratio} = \text{Total Debt} / \text{Total Equity}$	Shows the financial structure and potential risk from heavy borrowing; higher ratios imply greater risk.	Offers insight into financial leverage and risk; Affects equity return potential; Higher ratio improves equity returns.	High ratio implies financial risk; Vulnerable to interest rate fluctuations; Excessive debt can lead to financial distress.
Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR)	Measures the project's ability to cover debt obligations.	Ratio	$DSCR = \text{Net Operating Income} / \text{Total Debt Service}$	Important for ensuring the project can meet its debt obligations, often required by financiers.	Measures project ability to cover debt; Key for securing financing; Ensures long-term financial stability.	Lower DSCR implies higher financial risk; Highly leveraged projects may struggle to maintain DSCR; May exclude capital reinvestment needs.
Energy Yield Risk (EYR)	Quantifies the risk that the energy generated is lower than forecasted.	Percentage (%)	$EYR = (\text{Forecasted Energy} - \text{Actual Energy}) / \text{Forecasted Energy}$	Crucial for assessing whether the project will meet its expected financial and energy targets.	Identifies variability in energy production; Critical for assessing resource availability; Helps predict revenue shortfalls.	Hard to quantify accurately in variable climates; Affects long-term revenue predictability; High EYR can scare investors.
Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)	Average cost of capital weighted by the proportion of equity and debt financing.	Percentage (%)	$WACC = (E/V * Re) + ((D/V * Rd) * (1 - Tc))$	Essential for discounting cash flows in financial models, affecting project valuation and viability.	Reflects cost of financing; Critical for NPV and IRR; Considers debt and equity structure.	Sensitive to market fluctuations; Requires accurate input values; High WACC reduces NPV.

3.3. Discussion on Identified Criteria

This section has presented a comprehensive review of KPIs, it should be noted however that new KPIs are introduced, and our review has focused on KPIs most widely used in practice. The special nature of offshore wind energy projects with a long service life, front loaded investment needed, significant uncertainties in the resource which leads to uncertainties at the generated profits, and the complex technology that needs to operate at a high level of availability, introduce special requirements that yield for close monitoring of the performance of the asset as a structural system, a value generating entity as well as a part of a system that integrates multiple plants and technologies which should achieve to deliver the required electricity to the grid. As such, qualifying the most suitable KPIs is an essential task for developers and operators.

Summarising on the impact of the long service life of the assets, the degradation rate and system lifetime are crucial KPIs for monitoring the aging patterns of components over time. Low or controlled DRs are key to ensuring consistent performance reducing maintenance needs and OPEX. MTBF and availability help maintaining efficient operations and minimise downtime, assessing the robustness and dependability of the system. Finally, LCC, which captures CAPEX, OPEX and decommissioning costs helps operators maintain financial stability over the long term. For the front-loaded nature of the investment, indicators such as CAPEX and DPP are relevant as shorter DPPs imply a faster cost recovery and a reduced financial risk by accelerating ROI. The metrics of NPV and IRR are also vital in assessing the high upfront costs and the viability of investments through achieving a positive NPV or a competitive IRR. Finally, discussing on the uncertain nature of many of the contributing variables require careful monitoring of indicators such as CF or EYR comparing actual with theoretical outputs and measuring the risk of underperforming due to deviation from the initial forecast. CFaR evaluates the impact of inherent variability due to adverse and external conditions to the cashflows, quantifying financial uncertainties especially in the early stages of an investment. Availability is also an important KPI here as it can assess the resilience of the system not only to variable environmental conditions (such as prolonged weather windows), but also ensuring that obligations for power production are achieved, minimising OPEX and maximising profits.

4. Criteria Selection for Industrial Feasibility

4.1. Introduction

The previous two sections have presented a thorough analysis of technical and economic KPIs. Although the analysis is comprehensive, the reader is reminded that additional categories of KPIs for a complete assessment can be considered, such as social and environmental, which will be covered later in the project. Further, apart from the well-established indicators, additional criteria can be developed for specific purposes in the development and benchmarking of different technologies. In this chapter, we will make a brief reference to the specific problem of criteria selection for industrial feasibility, a topic that is closely related to the activities of Task 3.1 on the anchor assessment for FOW application, outcome of which will be documented in Deliverable D3.1. The purpose here is to distinguish a broad spectrum of criteria that can later be narrowed down to a manageable number of criteria that can be quantified through appropriate KPIs and combined with multicriteria analysis to qualify the prevailing decision alternative.

4.2. Criteria selection process

Selection of criteria for any decision-making problem is an important step and the analyst should ensure that sufficient analysis has taken place to distinguish a manageable number of non-overlapping criteria, without omitting any factor with significant influence to the decision making process (Kolios et al., 2016). Apart from using logic and knowledge from previous decision-making activities, review of literature and best practice guidelines from expert stakeholders can be employed. For problems like the one we are discussing in this section, a varying pool of stakeholders may be consulted including developers, local communities, environmental organizations, technology developers, to name a few, each offering a different perspective to the problem. Usually, the decision-making process is iterative, starting from a long list of criteria that can be consolidated and reduced to avoid duplication or an excessive list of criteria that requires significant resources to analyze.

For any decision-making problem, what is needed is a list of criteria, their corresponding weights, and a decision matrix where all decision alternatives are scored, through qualitative or quantitative means against each criterion (Lozano-Minguez et al., 2011). Focusing on the weights of criteria, although many analysts consider them as carrying equal weight, this is an oversimplification that can skew results. To this end, certain approaches can be followed for the assignment of appropriate relative weights of importance to each of the criteria, such as the following (Azman et al., 2023; Bödefeld & Marsili, 2023; Mat Kasim & Jemain, 2020; ROSZKOWSKA, 2020; Shureshjani, 2021):

- Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)
- Entropy Method
- Direct Assignment or Expert Judgment

- Rank Order Centroid (ROC)
- Swing Weighting Method
- Best Worst Method (BWM)
- Fuzzy AHP
- Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique (SMART)

4.3. Long List of Criteria for Industrial Feasibility Evaluation

In this section, a long list of criteria for industrial feasibility evaluation is presented, able to support the evaluation of a number of problems related to offshore renewable energy innovations.

Figure 2: Long List of Criteria

The criteria listed above can indeed be linked to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) identified earlier in chapter 3, towards a more quantitative assessment of the different options, since KPIs can quantify impact in measurable terms. For example, the criterion of Fabrication and Manufacturing which evaluates the complexity and cost of fabricating a component can be linked with the KPIs of Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX). Quantification of criteria, although requires more data and resources for the assessment, can provide the basis for better informed decisions from stakeholders and reduce bias of the qualitative scoring. Table 13, provides this linkage between feasibility criteria, with a short description, and the corresponding KPIs. It is important to mention that there is not one way to bridge the two lists, criteria and KPIs, as this would depend on the interpretation of the criteria and the type of problem that needs to be solved, however the table below provides a reasonable correlation.

Table 13: Linking Feasibility Criteria with KPIs

Feasibility Criteria	Description	Related KPIs
<i>Material Sustainability</i>	Focuses on the environmental impact, recyclability, and durability of materials used.	Total Lifecycle Cost (LCC), Degradation Rate (DR)
<i>Fabrication and Manufacturing</i>	Evaluates the ease, cost, and complexity of component production and assembly.	Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), Operational Expenditure (OPEX)
<i>Transportation and Logistics</i>	Assesses the cost and feasibility of transporting components from production to installation.	Cost of Risk (CoR)
<i>Installation Efficiency</i>	Measures the cost, time, and challenges related to component installation.	Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), Availability (A)
<i>Design Life and Durability</i>	Focuses on the expected operational lifespan and resistance to wear and failure.	Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), System Lifetime (SL)
<i>Decommissioning and Recyclability</i>	Evaluates the ease, cost, and environmental impact of decommissioning components.	Decommissioning Costs (as part of LCC)
<i>Impact on Marine Environment</i>	Assesses the impact of installation and operation on marine ecosystems.	To be covered in D5.1
<i>Economic Opportunities</i>	Evaluates potential benefits to local economies, including job creation.	Return on Investment (ROI), Profitability Index (PI)
<i>Technical Performance</i>	Focuses on the functional capabilities and effectiveness of components under different conditions.	Capacity Factor (CF), Effective Load-Carrying Capability (ELCC)
<i>Scalability</i>	Assesses the potential for scaling production and deployment.	Flexibility and Grid Stability (Response Time)
<i>Regulatory Compliance</i>	Ensures compliance with international and local regulations and standards.	To be covered in D5.1
<i>Innovation and Technological Advancement</i>	Evaluates the incorporation of advanced materials and technology to enhance performance.	System Inertia (SI), Ramp Rate (RR)
<i>Cost and Economic Viability</i>	Assesses the total cost of the project in terms of installation, operation, and energy production.	Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Discounted Payback Period (DPP)
<i>Operational Efficiency</i>	Focuses on system performance during operation, including reliability and uptime.	Availability (A), Energy Efficiency (Eeff)
<i>Safety and Risk Management</i>	Ensures safety during installation and operation while minimizing risks of failure.	Forced Outage Rate (FOR), Equivalent Forced Outage Rate (EFOR)
<i>Social and Community Impact</i>	Evaluates the effects on local communities, including acceptance and benefits.	To be covered in D5.1
<i>Supply Chain and Market Factors</i>	Assesses the reliability of suppliers and broader market dynamics impacting feasibility.	Market and External Support KPIs, Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DtE)
<i>Flexibility and Adaptability</i>	Evaluates the system's ability to adapt to different conditions and integrate with other technologies.	Curtailment Ratio (CR), Flexibility and Grid Stability (SI)

5. Benchmarking Study Based on KPIs

5.1. Benchmarking Criteria

The benchmarking process carried out in this study is designed to assess different configurations of offshore platforms, sites, and mooring systems based on a set of well-defined criteria. These criteria include technical, economic, and operational performance metrics, which together provide a comprehensive view of system suitability across various environmental and operational contexts. By assigning a score to each configuration for every criterion, this benchmarking allows for a comparative analysis that brings to light the relative strengths and weaknesses of each setup. Table 14 below presents a reduced list of KPIs which are suitable for the benchmarking of different technological solutions. In our assessment we employ a semi-quantitative approach, assigning a score of 1-5 for each of the criteria, together with a reasoning behind each score. A score of 1 denotes the least favourable option for each of the criteria, while a score of 5 the opposite. Table 15 presents a list of the scoring system for each of the criteria. Note that the purpose of this benchmarking is illustrative focusing more on showing the approach and identifying the key system properties rather than on pointing to the most suitable technologies of a given floating offshore wind scenario. The scoring of each alternative against each of the criteria was given according to the best knowledge of the authors, combining expert opinions, published literature and real-world data. This approach is deemed sufficient for the objectives set and the current state of the project. In future project activities, the experience of the TAILWIND consortium members will provide an important source of information, ensuring a well-informed scoring process. As stated below some scenarios may not be strictly realistic but were nevertheless considered in the study to test the approach.

Table 14: Qualifying list of technical and economic KPIs

Criterion	Reasoning
Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)	Reflects system reliability; higher MTBF indicates fewer disruptions, critical for consistent energy production and reduced maintenance.
Unplanned Downtime (UD)	Measures unexpected offline periods; reduced downtime ensures continuous energy generation and minimizes economic losses.
Availability (A)	Indicates the proportion of operational time; high availability ensures optimal use of capacity, contributing to revenue and profitability.
Degradation Rate (DR)	Tracks performance deterioration; lower degradation rates indicate greater durability and lower maintenance needs over time.
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Represents upfront investment; reducing CAPEX while maintaining performance enhances financial attractiveness of projects.
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Accounts for ongoing costs; innovations that lower OPEX (e.g., through increased reliability) improve economic viability.
Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)	Combines CAPEX, OPEX, and energy output; a holistic measure of cost-efficiency and competitiveness for energy projects.
Project Life (System Lifetime)	Reflects operational duration; longer lifetimes reduce replacements, spread CAPEX, and lower LCOE, improving sustainability and value.

Table 15: List of criteria with scoring interpretation

Criterion	Key Considerations	Scoring Interpretation
Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)	Reflects system reliability; higher scores denote more reliable configurations.	<i>Score = 1:</i> High-risk systems (e.g., challenging environmental conditions, less durable materials, complex configurations prone to failure). <i>Score = 3:</i> Moderate reliability (e.g., proven materials and designs but with moderate risk due to depth or platform complexity). <i>Score = 5:</i> Highly reliable systems (e.g., simple configurations, robust materials, low-risk sites).
Unplanned Downtime (UD)	Measures predictability of performance; lower downtime results in higher scores.	<i>Lower scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios involving soft materials under high stress (e.g., TLP platforms), or stiff materials in shallow water. <i>Higher scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios involving robust materials under high stress (e.g., TLP platforms), or soft materials under moderate tensions (e.g., semi-submersible).
Availability (A)	Accounts for ease of maintenance and system readiness; higher scores indicate more accessible systems.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios with shallow sites, less suitable materials, or highly tensioned configurations, which complicate maintenance processes and reduce availability. <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios with robust materials, in intermediate waters, or configurations with simpler maintenance procedures.
Degradation Rate (DR)	Evaluates material durability and resistance to environmental stresses; lower degradation results in higher scores.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios involving soft materials under high tension, leading to rapid degradation. <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios involving robust materials (e.g., hard composites or steel) that degrade slowly, even under challenging conditions.
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Considers upfront investment; lower costs result in higher scores.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios involving expensive materials (e.g., steel, hard composites) or complex configurations (e.g., TLP, deep waters). <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios with soft materials or shallow water installations, reducing both material and installation costs.
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Examines ongoing costs; lower operational expenses result in higher scores.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios with less suitable materials under high tension or in deep waters, requiring frequent maintenance and increasing costs. <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios with suitable materials with well-known properties in shallow water configurations, minimizing maintenance and operational challenges.
Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)	Combines CAPEX and OPEX to measure cost per energy unit; lower costs yield higher scores.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios with expensive materials (steel, hard composites) in deep or high-tension configurations. <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios with soft or chain materials in shallow waters, which reduce both CAPEX and OPEX.
Project Life (System Lifetime)	Reflects operational longevity; higher scores indicate extended system lifespans.	<i>Low Scores (1-2):</i> Scenarios involving soft materials under high tension or stiff materials in shallow waters, leading to reduced nominal lifespans. <i>High Scores (4-5):</i> Scenarios involving robust materials (e.g., chain, hard composites, steel) under high tensions or soft materials in shallow waters, which significantly extend system lifetime.

5.2. Scenarios of Different Configurations

For the benchmarking study, we are considering a list of scenarios developed earlier in WP1. Each scenario presents a separate configuration combining a type of platform, a site with certain water-depth, a mooring system concept and mooring line materials. Table 16 below, summarises all scenarios.

Table 16: Scenarios for Benchmarking

Scenario ID	Platform	Site	Mooring Concept
1	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
2	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
3	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
3b	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
4	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
5	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
6	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Chain
7	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
8	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
9	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
10	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
10b	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
11	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Steel
12	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
13	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
14	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Steel
15	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
16	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
17	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Steel
18	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)
19	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Hard (Aramid, Dyneema)
20	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 10 m)	Steel

The semisubmersible platform configuration is one of the most widely developed technologies, suitable for both shallow and deep water locations. Its design is valued for its stability and versatility, and it can be paired with a range of mooring materials, including chain moorings and soft (e.g., Nylon, Polyester) or harder (e.g., Aramid, Dyneema) materials. In shallower waters, such as the ~100-meter depth at Provence Grand Large, simpler and more cost-effective moorings are often preferred due to their reduced geometric stiffness and shorter line lengths, which can lead to higher loads in certain configurations. In contrast, deeper waters like Utsira Nord at 256 meters may require more robust mooring materials to address specific design considerations, though these depths typically do not impose stresses as significant as those encountered in ultra-deep-water moorings exceeding thousands of meters.

Tension Leg Platforms (TLPs) is the second configuration which is best suited to deeper waters, and although more difficult to implement, they need mooring systems with appropriate materials to sustain the high pretension stresses. For both deployment sites,

TLPs will be coupled with steep, hard composites and soft materials, aiming to balance performance and cost.

Finally, the Tension Leg Buoys (TLBs), offer an intermediate solution which combines adaptability of the semi-subs and stability of TLPs. As such, it can be deployed in both shallow and deeper waters and can be combined with different mooring materials, however the concept requires selection of durable material for high-tension setups.

Note that in deliverables 1.1 and 1.3 soft materials were excluded for TLP and TLB since these platforms need high stiffness materials such as Dyneema and Aramid to keep place. These are still considered in this study out of completeness to test the approach in as many different scenarios as possible.

5.3. Analysis of Benchmarking Study

Table 17: Benchmarking assessment

Scenario ID	Platform	Site	Mooring Concept	Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)		Unplanned Downtime (UD)		Availability (A)		Degradation Rate (DR)		Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)		Operational Expenditure (OPEX)		Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)		Project Life (System Lifetime)		Score
1	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	4	Soft materials reduce loads, multiple materials increase complexity.	4	Soft materials reduce the likelihood of unexpected failures at depth.	4	Soft materials require less frequent inspections, multiple components increase complexity	3	Soft materials are prone to degradation, but stresses are limited.	4	Soft materials reduce upfront costs, though deep depth increases installation expenses.	3	Soft materials require less frequent maintenance, water depth increases spendings on inspections and maintenance.	3	Soft materials lower CAPEX but higher OPEX increases LCOE.	5	Soft materials under low stresses give high nominal lifetimes.	30
2	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	2	Stiff materials increase loads, multiple materials increase complexity.	2	Stiff materials under high stress increase failure unpredictability.	2	Stiff materials require frequent inspection and maintenance.	4	Stiff materials have better resistance to wear and marine conditions.	2	Stiff materials are expensive, and deep sites further increase CAPEX.	2	Stiff materials require more frequent maintenance, increasing ongoing costs.	2	High CAPEX and high OPEX increase LCOE for stiff materials at depth.	2	Stiff materials increase stresses, reducing nominal lifetime.	18
3	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	3	Similar to Scenario 1; semi-taut system increases stress in lines.	3	Similar to Scenario 1; semi-taut system increases risk of unplanned downtime.	4	Similar to Scenario 1.	3	Same as Scenario 1; soft materials degrade more quickly than stiff materials.	4	Similar to Scenario 1; cost-effective soft mooring materials.	3	Same as Scenario 1; operational challenges with soft materials at depth.	3	Similar to Scenario 1; soft materials result in moderate LCOE.	5	Same as Scenario 1; soft materials reduce stresses.	28
3b	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	4	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	4	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	5	Same reasoning as Scenario 3.	28
4	Semisubmersible	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	2	Stiff materials reduces reliability of semi-taut mooring lines.	3	Stiff materials increase stress, increasing downtime risk.	2	Similar to Scenario 2.	4	Stiff materials have better resistance to wear and marine conditions.	2	Expensive stiff materials and deep water drive up CAPEX.	2	Stiff materials increase operational costs at deep depths.	2	High upfront and operational costs increase LCOE for this configuration.	2	Stiff materials reduce longevity in challenging conditions.	19

5	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	4	Shallower depth increases stress on mooring lines, reducing reliability.	4	Shallower depth increase stress, increasing unpredictability.	4	Shallower depth eases access.	2	Shallow depth increases degradation, and soft materials are still less durable.	5	Shallow depth and soft materials minimize installation and material costs.	4	Shallower depth mitigates some maintenance challenges.	5	Shallow depth and soft materials reduce CAPEX and OPEX, lowering LCOE.	3	Shallower depth increases stress, reducing the lifetime of soft materials.	31
6	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Chain	3	Chain moorings are challenging at shallow depths, providing low reliability.	4	Chain mooring inspection is more reliable, minimizing unexpected system failures.	5	Chain moorings are highly maintainable in shallow depths.	5	Chain moorings are highly durable and degrade slowly in shallow conditions.	3	Chain materials are moderately priced, but installation is cheaper in shallow waters.	5	Chain moorings are durable with well-know inspection intervals in shallow water.	4	Chain moorings are moderately cost-effective in shallow waters, resulting in reasonable LCOE.	4	Chain moorings are highly durable, but lifetime is limited by shallow waters.	33
7	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	4	Similar to Scenario 5; shallow depth increases material stress.	4	Same as Scenario 5; soft materials fare better at shallow depths.	5	Same as Scenario 5; shallow depth mitigates some maintenance challenges.	2	Similar to Scenario 5; shallower depth increases degradation risks.	5	Same as Scenario 5; soft materials and shallow waters reduce costs.	4	Same as Scenario 5; reduced operational costs due to shallow site.	4	Similar to Scenario 5; lower costs reduce LCOE.	3	Similar to Scenario 5; moderate lifetime improvement due to shallow depth.	31
8	Semisubmersible	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	2	Stiff materials increase stress, especially at this shallow depth.	2	Stiff materials and shallow water depth increases downtime risk.	3	Similar to scenario 2, shallow depths reduces maintenance challenges.	4	Same as Scenario 4.	3	Stiff materials are expensive but mitigated by shallow water installation.	3	Stiff materials require frequent inspections, but shallow water reduces costs.	3	Stiff materials slightly increase CAPEX, leading to moderate LCOE.	2	Stiff materials in shallow conditions limit system lifetime.	22
9	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	2	TLB platforms require higher tension, increasing failure risk for soft materials.	2	Soft materials in TLB platforms under high tension lead to unexpected risks.	2	Soft materials in high-tension configurations are difficult to maintain.	1	High tension causes significant wear and tear on soft materials.	3	TLB platforms increase CAPEX due to higher tension requirements.	1	High tension combined with soft materials increases maintenance and downtime.	2	High tension and deep depth increase OPEX, raising LCOE.	3	High tension results in accelerated wear and shorter lifespan.	16
10	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	5	Stiff materials perform well under TLB and intermediate water depths.	4	Stiff materials reduce risk but do not fully eliminate it in TLB configurations.	3	Moderate maintainability, though tension complicates access.	5	Stiff materials provide excellent durability in intermediate depths.	2	High tension and expensive stiff materials drive up CAPEX.	3	Stiff materials reduce costs, but tension still requires periodic maintenance.	2	High CAPEX and OPEX due to tension and expensive materials increase LCOE.	5	Stiff materials extend lifetime but are still affected by high tension.	29
10b	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	5	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	4	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	5	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	2	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	3	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	2	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	5	Same reasoning as Scenario 10.	29

11	TLB	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Steel	5	Steel moorings provide excellent durability and reliability at this depth.	5	Steel provides robust, predictable performance, minimizing downtime.	4	Steel moorings offer durability and moderate maintainability at depth.	5	Steel provides the best resistance to degradation under deep, high-tension conditions.	2	Steel materials are expensive, and high-tension configurations increase costs.	4	Steel provides durability, reducing long-term maintenance costs.	2	Steel materials and deep water tension increase both CAPEX and OPEX.	5	Steel provides the longest nominal lifetime even in challenging environments.	32
12	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	2	Same reasoning as scenario 9. Low water depth reduces reliability	3	Increased risk of downtime due to material elongation under TLB tension.	3	Soft materials in high-tension configurations are difficult to maintain.	2	Soft materials degrade moderately under TLB tension, even at shallow depth.	4	Shallow depth and soft materials reduce installation and material costs.	2	High tension combined with soft materials increases maintenance and inspections.	3	Moderate costs for soft materials reduce but do not minimize LCOE.	2	Moderate lifetime reduction due to increased stress in shallow waters.	21
13	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	4	Stiff materials improve reliability but higher tension and shallow water remains a concern.	4	Stiff materials reduce risk but do not fully eliminate it in TLB configurations.	5	Stiff materials simplify maintenance in shallow water configurations.	3	Moderate durability under high tension; stiff materials resist degradation better.	3	Stiff materials increase costs despite the shallow depth.	4	Stiff materials in shallow depths minimize maintenance needs.	4	Stiff materials increase CAPEX slightly but low OPEX keeps LCOE manageable.	4	Stiff materials ensure long lifetime, despite shallow water configurations.	31
14	TLB	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Steel	4	Steel moorings ensure excellent reliability, but shallow water remains a concern	4	Steel ensures minimal downtime under TLB loads, shallow water increases unpredictability in downtime.	5	Steel moorings offer excellent durability and easy maintenance.	5	Steel ensures low degradation at TLB tension, shallow water increased degradation.	2	Steel moorings are expensive despite shallow water cost savings.	5	Steel ensures minimal operational costs in shallow water configurations.	3	Steel materials increase costs slightly despite shallow depth.	4	Steel components ensure long lifetime even in shallow water conditions.	32
15	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	2	Same reasoning as scenario 9	2	High pretension and depth create unpredictable risks for soft materials.	1	High pretension and depth make soft materials extremely difficult to maintain.	2	Soft materials degrade moderately at intermediate depths under TLP tension.	3	TLP configurations are expensive, though soft materials reduce material costs.	1	High pretension and depth significantly increase maintenance requirements.	2	High tension and deep water increase operational costs, raising LCOE.	2	High pretension results in significantly reduced system lifetime.	15
16	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	4	Stiff materials improve reliability but high tension remains a concern.	4	Stiff materials improve predictability, though tension adds some risk.	3	Stiff materials ease maintenance somewhat but depth and tension remain challenging.	5	Stiff materials are resistant to degradation in intermediate depths.	2	Stiff materials and TLP pretension requirements lead to high CAPEX.	3	Stiff materials reduce costs, though pretension remains an operational factor.	2	High CAPEX and OPEX for stiff materials and TLP configurations increase LCOE.	4	Stiff materials improve lifetime, but pretension limits longevity.	27

17	TLP	Utsira Nord (Depth 256 m)	Steel	5	Steel moorings offer the highest reliability under TLP configurations.	5	Steel materials provide the most robust and predictable performance.	4	Steel offers reliability, though tension complicates maintenance at depth.	5	Steel ensures excellent durability in intermediate depths under TLP conditions.	2	Steel and TLP configurations incur high material and installation costs.	4	Steel materials lower long-term costs despite high pretension.	2	Steel under TLP tension and deep conditions results in high LCOE.	5	Steel ensures the longest system lifetime under high pretension conditions.	32
18	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Soft (Nylon, Polyester)	2	TLB platforms require higher tension, increasing failure risk for soft materials.	2	High risk due to material stress under high pretension and shallow water.	2	Similar to scenario 15, although reduced depth simplifies access	2	High pretension results in rapid degradation of soft materials.	4	Shallow depth and soft materials reduce CAPEX for TLP systems.	2	Shallow water reduces operational challenges but soft materials remain costly.	2	Shallow depth mitigates some costs but TLP tension keeps LCOE moderate.	2	Same as scenario 15.	18
19	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Stiff (Aramid, Dyneema)	4	Stiff materials ensure excellent reliability in TLP, shallow depth reduces reliability.	4	Stiff materials minimize unplanned downtime, shallow water increases unpredictability in downtime.	5	Stiff materials in shallow depths ensure easy maintenance.	3	Stiff materials are more durable but are affected by high tension.	3	Stiff materials remain moderately expensive even at shallow depths.	4	Stiff materials in shallow depths minimize maintenance and operational costs.	4	Stiff materials and shallow depth result in manageable LCOE.	4	Stiff materials ensure long lifespan in shallow TLP configurations.	31
20	TLP	Provence Grand Large (Depth 100 m)	Steel	4	Steel moorings are the most reliable option for TLP, shallow depth reduces reliability.	4	Steel ensures maximum predictability, shallow water increases unpredictability in downtime.	5	Steel provides excellent maintainability in shallow water configurations.	5	Steel provides the highest resistance to degradation under TLP conditions.	2	Steel and TLP configurations remain costly despite shallow depths.	5	Steel ensures the lowest operational costs in shallow waters.	3	Steel slightly increases costs despite shallow site benefits.	4	Steel components provide the longest lifetime in shallow water conditions.	32

5.4. Discussion on outcomes

The benchmarking study for floating offshore wind systems highlights platform performance based on materials, site depth, and configurations.

Semisubmersibles in shallow waters (e.g., Provence Grand Large) with soft or chain moorings achieved high scores due to cost efficiency, ease of maintenance, and durability, especially for chain moorings (Scenario 6, Score: 33). In deep waters (Utsira Nord), semisubmersibles with soft materials (Scenario 1, Score: 30) performed moderately well due to reduced costs but faced higher operational expenditures.

Tension Leg Buoy (TLB) systems demonstrated significant variance. In deep waters, soft materials (Scenario 9, Score: 16) exhibited poor performance due to high pretension and material degradation, while steel moorings (Scenario 11, Score: 32) provided excellent reliability and durability despite high costs. In shallow waters, TLB configurations using steel (Scenario 14, Score: 32) excelled due to low operational costs and long system lifetimes.

Tension Leg Platform (TLP) configurations encountered challenges, particularly with soft materials (Scenarios 15 and 18), which scored poorly due to high pretension stress and rapid material degradation. Steel moorings (Scenario 17, Score: 32) and stiff materials (Scenario 19, Score: 31) improved performance with enhanced reliability and lifespan, though at higher costs.

Key findings include the superiority of chain and steel moorings in shallow and deep-water scenarios, respectively, due to their balance of reliability and operational efficiency. Soft materials excel in cost-effective shallow-water setups but underperform in high-tension environments. Stiff materials and steel, while costly, offer robustness and longevity essential for demanding configurations.

Recommendations emphasize using chain or soft materials for shallow waters and steel or stiff materials for deep waters or high-tension platforms, balancing CAPEX, OPEX, and LCOE to maximize reliability and sustainability.

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable reports findings of Task 1.2, and focuses on a comprehensive review of KPIs that are available in literature and can support developers assess the technical and economic performance of wind turbines, components, innovations and investments. The review has returned many indicators that have been categorised appropriately and can offer quantifiable measures of performance. The KPIs identified, have also been linked with criteria to assess industrial feasibility of technological solutions. Finally, an indicative, high level benchmarking study of different configurations of platforms, deployment sites, mooring systems and materials of mooring lines has been presented, drawing useful insights on the importance of customising mooring solutions to different configuration and deployment environment.

The work reported herein, will inform activities of WP3 and WP5, and will be extended further in deliverable D5.1, where environmental and social KPIs will also be covered towards a fully comprehensive review of multi-disciplinary KPIs. The importance of considering multiple KPIs cannot be overstated, as modern auctions move beyond the least-LCOE approach to account for sustainability performance, aggregating economic, social and environmental dimensions of proposed investments. Specifically, for the TAILWIND project, this review is important as it will allow a multi-dimensional assessment of the impact of specific innovations and the project as a whole.

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